

The Influence Of Customer Perspectives Related To Business Ethics On Customer Loyalty In The Shopee Market Place

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of a customer perspective on business ethics on customer loyalty in the Shopee marketplace. The results of the study show that having a good customer perspective will lead to increased customer loyalty to the Shopee Marketplace itself. This study uses qualitative research methods with data collection techniques through observation and questionnaires.

INTRODUCTION

Technological advances in the current era encourage Indonesia to make changes. Where technology is a mechanism that drives change, humans will always try to maintain and adapt to nature which is constantly updated by technology (Martono, 2014). The development of technology encourages major changes in various aspects of life. From the economic aspect, the interest of the Indonesian people has shifted to online marketplaces, whereby this helps people to be able to shop more practically, easily and more efficiently.

Changes made by the Indonesian nation continued, until in 1999 e-commerce emerged by Andrew Darwis, by introducing the KASKUS forum, where this forum became the first online buying and selling place and then followed by other online buying and selling forums. The development of E-Commerce is moving rapidly, this is due to people who are familiar with the internet widely, and the government's awareness of the potential created to bring development to society, the fate of shops, markets and conventional stalls. The emergence of online buying and selling sites in 2015, such as: Shopee, Lazada, Tokopedia and so on became the end of the KASKUS forum, because this year e-commerce has reached its peak and is widely known by the public

(Mustajibah & Trilaksana, 2021).The following graph of online marketplace users can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Graph of Online Marketplace Application Users

Source : Databoks 2022

Figure 1.1 can be seen that the interest of online marketplace users has increased every year, various kinds of marketplaces are competing to get the highest ratings in sales. The buying and selling channel model that is becoming a trend at the moment is buying and selling online. This system beats conventional buying and selling. Where online marketplaces prioritize the convenience of shopping, the completeness of needed goods, and the many discounts offered present a great appeal to the wider community. One of the dominant online marketplaces in Indonesia is the Shopee marketplace. Shopee has been operating since 2015 led by Chris Feng who is part of the SEA Group, and whose head office is in Singapore. Shopee is an online shopping center that offers various types of products ranging from electronics, books, children's toys, baby equipment, medical devices and beauty products, household appliances, traveling equipment, sports equipment, and others. In addition, Shopee offers easy shopping solutions for consumers who want to buy goods online by displaying online reviews and online ratings to increase trust for consumers and potential customers.

Problems that often arise in buying and selling at the Many problems experienced by consumers when shopping at the Shopee Marketplace affect customer confidence to shop at the Shopee marketplace, which has an impact on the level of customer loyalty. Where the company's success is marked by the number of loyal customers. The longer the loyalty of a customer, the greater the profit a customer can get from that company (Supertini, Telagawathi, & Yulianthini, 2020). The problems with Shopee are caused by several parties. The first is from the seller, like the many frauds committed by the seller in the marketplace shopee just to make a profit, starting from deceiving customers by providing images that do not match the items available. The second is from the delivery service, for example the delay in the ordered goods not according to the estimated time specified, or even the goods not reaching the customer, and the carelessness of the delivery service which causes the goods to be damaged. And finally, from the Shopee marketplace, for example, Shopee is not strict with

violators of its policies, and does not provide more detailed guidelines regarding policies for sellers.

There are many frauds committed by sellers in the shopee marketplace just for profit, starting from deceiving customers by providing images that do not match the items available. This greatly deviates from the application of business ethics in buying and selling transactions. According to Satyanugraha ethics are values and moral norms in society. In this sense, ethics is the same as morality or morality, namely what must be done and what cannot be done, in which case ethics is considered a science that has a tradition. While business is a business activity selling goods and services to consumers to meet needs. Meanwhile, business ethics itself, according to Straub and Atter, business is an organization that carries out production and sales activities of goods and services desired by consumers to obtain profit (Badroen, 2006).

In every activity, there are certain rules that must be obeyed, and in the Shopee marketplace there are also ethics that must be followed so that the business runs well. Without ethics in the Shopee marketplace, competition between marketplaces can become unhealthy, consumers are harmed, environmental pollution or the emergence of monopoly practices. The application of business ethics to the Shopee marketplace is a guide in determining whether or not an action is taken by the Shopee marketplace in carrying out its business. The good service provided by the Shopee marketplace causes customer trust in the Shopee marketplace, which affects customer satisfaction and is able to increase customer loyalty.

According to Jasfar, customer trust is a very powerful weapon in building relationships because the high level of customer trust from a company makes the company strong in building relationships with customers. This is in line with Wahyu Nugroho's theory, that the relationship between trust and customer loyalty is that the higher the customer's trust in a product, the higher the level of customer loyalty to a brand. Nuraini stated that loyal customers are those who are very satisfied with a particular product so they have the enthusiasm to introduce it to anyone they know. Furthermore, these loyal customers will extend their 'loyalty' to other products made by the same manufacturer. In the end, they are loyal consumers to the next producer. Another important element of loyalty is the support for a product or service that is embodied in communication one's positive experience. One of the strongest persuasions is someone's words.

The good point of view of customers towards a marketplace as a supporter of trust in new consumers who will shop at a particular marketplace (R, 2013). Based on the background explanation above, we therefore took the title of research on "The Influence of Customer Perspective Related to Business Ethics on Customer Loyalty in the Shopee Marketplace".

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

A. Customer Perspective (X)

According to Hartati, the customer perspective is the level of customer satisfaction based on the Service Quality theory which includes statements regarding:

- a. *Tangibility* namely the respondent's comments on the shopee application
- b. *Reality* or reliability is the ability of Shopee to provide services to customers, whether it is in accordance with business ethics.
- c. *Responsiveness* is the ability of shopee employees to provide fast and precise service
- d. *assurance* is the respondent's perception of assurance or certainty which includes knowledge, courtesy and the ability of Shopee employees to foster a sense of trust in the respondent
- e. Empathy is the respondent's response to personal or individual attention given by Shopee.

Renanda stated the customer perspective related to the way a company serves its customers. In this case, every customer must be treated properly or properly so that customers get a sense of satisfaction with the services provided by the company. The existence of good service can increase consumer loyalty to the company. On the other hand, if the company provides poor service, the customer will definitely look for another company that has better service. Measures that companies can apply from a customer perspective are:

1. How big is the sales turnover.
2. The level of profit earned by the company.
3. How many customers did you get.
4. Percentage of customer loyalty to the product.
5. Customer satisfaction level.
6. customer needs.

Business ethics has a close relationship with the customer perspective which will describe how satisfied a customer is with a business service. Business ethics provide an incentive for customers to establish strong relationships with the company's business. In the long term, this kind of bond allows the company to thoroughly understand customer expectations and their needs. Thus the company is able to increase the level of satisfaction customers, in which the company maximizes the pleasant customer experience and minimizes the less pleasant customer experience.

The goal of a business is to make consumers feel satisfied. Superior and consistent service quality can foster customer satisfaction and will provide various benefits. The customer perspective is the response of consumers to the actual performance that is felt after experiencing the service of a business. The factor that will determine satisfaction here is the customer's perspective regarding the application of business ethics which focuses on three dimensions of business ethics, namely: honesty, fairness and truth. Consumers in choosing a product or service do not only depend on the quality of service, but also depend on the value felt by consumers, companies must add value that can

make consumers get what they pay for or more than they expect, so that consumers can survive.

B. Customer loyalty

Loyalty is literally interpreted as one's loyalty to an object. Or interpreted as a situation where consumers have a positive attitude and have a commitment to a brand, and have a commitment and intend to continue their purchases in the future. According to Fleming, customer loyalty is the attitude and satisfaction of customers to keep using a particular service. Gitomer stated that loyalty is a manifestation of the fundamental human need to belong, support, gain a sense of security and build attachment as well as create an emotional attachment. Customer loyalty is a customer's commitment to a brand, store or supplier based on a very positive trait in long-term purchases. Shaw and Hamilton stated that customer loyalty is the result of positive emotional experiences that are consistently felt by customers. Customer loyalty is the result of customer satisfaction based on certain aspects that give rise to a feeling of satisfaction with an item or service ordered. With this satisfaction then become loyal customers to a particular store or brand. Loyal customers are people who:

1. Make regular repeat purchases
2. Buying across product and service lines
3. Referring to others
4. Demonstrates immunity to the pull of competitors.

According to Timm, customer loyalty is a customer who always makes repeated purchases, which in turn guarantees a stream of income for the company, has a tendency to buy more and is willing to pay a higher price, which has a direct impact on the profits the company gets. The concept of customer loyalty is more associated with behavior and attitude is a feeling shown by a customer after using a product or service. Purchases are made from time to time if a customer already has loyalty to a product.

Mardalis stated that there are several other factors that affect customer loyalty, namely: customer satisfaction, service quality and image. Customer satisfaction is a person's feeling of liking or disliking a product after he has compared the performance of the product with his expectations. Customer satisfaction as a positive response to the evaluation of experience in using a product or service. One important factor that can make customers satisfied is the quality of service. Marketers can improve low quality will run the risk of disloyal customers. If quality is considered and strengthened by advertising, customer loyalty will be easier to obtain and can even increase customer loyalty. Because loyal customers are those who are very satisfied with certain products or services in a marketplace so they have the enthusiasm to introduce them to anyone they know. Nurullaili and Wijayanto stated that image is a set of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person has towards an object. "A person's attitude and actions towards objects are highly conditioned by the image of the object". Someone who has a high impression and trust in a product

will not think long about buying and using a product and might even become a loyal customer. "A person's attitude and actions towards objects are highly conditioned by the image of the object". Someone who has a high impression and trust in a product will not think long about buying and using a product and might even become a loyal customer. "A person's attitude and actions towards objects are highly conditioned by the image of the object". Someone who has a high impression and trust in a product will not think long about buying and using a product and might even become a loyal customer.

According to Griffin, customer loyalty is more associated with behavior (behavior) than with attitude. If someone is a loyal customer, the consumer will show purchases that are defined as non-random purchases that are expressed from time to time by several decision-making units. Two important conditions related to loyalty are:

1. Customer retention (customer retention) describes the length of relationship with customers. The customer retention rate is the percentage of customers who have fulfilled a certain number of repeat purchases over a limited period of time.
2. The total share of customers (total share of costumer) of a company shows the percentage of the customer's budget spent on the company.

Customer loyalty to a marketplace is based on subscription motives. Where customers prioritize shopping on their trusted marketplace. The factors for the existence of a subscription motive are:

1. Trust
2. Classification and variety of goods
3. The seller's location is strategic and easy to reach
4. Store physical design
5. Services offered to customers
6. Salesperson skills
7. Advertising and sales promotion in store

Customer loyalty includes post-purchase consumer behavior. Loyal customers must go through the buying process first. Setiadi stated that the buying process consists of the following sequence:

1. Recognize a need
2. Information search
3. Alternative evaluation
4. Purchase satisfaction
5. Post purchase behavior.

A person becomes loyal to a product in the marketplace through several stages. This process lasts quite a long time, where each stage has different needs. With emphasis and attention at each stage, the marketplace has a great opportunity to mold potential buyers into loyal customers. Tjiptono put forward six indicators to measure customer loyalty, namely:

1. Repeat purchase
2. Habit of consuming the brand
3. Always loved the brand
4. It remains to choose the brand

5. Confident that the brand is the best
6. Recommend the brand to others.

Griffin explained the benefits that will be obtained if you have loyal customers:

1. Reducing marketing costs (because attracting new customers is more expensive)
2. Reduce transaction costs
3. Reducing consumer turn-over costs
4. Increase cross sales which will enlarge a company's market share
5. More positive word of mouth, assuming that loyal customers are also satisfied.
6. Reducing failure costs (such as replacement costs and others).

After the customer makes a purchase and finds purchase satisfaction, the consumer will compare the perceived reality with his expectations. The results lead to customer satisfaction or not to a product.

C. The Effect of Customer Perspective on Customer Loyalty in the Shopee Marketplace

From the theory above, the relationship between the customer perspective (X) and customer loyalty (Y) is that there is a relationship between the customer perspective regarding business ethics and customer loyalty in the Shopee marketplace. From Variable X has the following statements: Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy from the customer towards the Shopee application. And from the Y variable, loyalty is a customer's commitment to a store, brand or supplier based on a positive attitude which is reflected in the form of consistent repeated purchases. So having a good customer perspective will lead to increased customer loyalty to the Shopee Marketplace itself.

And this is related to one of the theories of business ethics, namely the Theory of Ethics of duty (Theory of Ethical Obligation), which is the forerunner of this obligation can be traced to the thoughts of the German philosopher, Immanuel Kant. Ethics is also known as deontology, a term taken from the Greek word deon which means obligation (duty). This ethic argues that an action contains moral values and is morally good if it is based on good motivation. An act is good if it is done because of good motivation based on obligation. For Kant, an action is good if it is done based on a categorical imperative, that is, an obligation that is carried out without any conditions. If someone lent an item, for example, then he is obliged to return it without having to fear being fined or not being reported to the authorities. The return of loaned goods is carried out strictly on the basis of obligation.

RESEARCH METHODS

A. TYPE AND RESEARCH APPROACH

This study uses a qualitative approach, which according to Sugiono qualitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism, used to research on natural object conditions, (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive/qualitative in nature, and qualitative results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

In this study there are two variables, research variables are everything in any form that is determined by researchers to be studied so that information about these variables is obtained then conclusions are drawn. In this research can be designed as follows:

1. Independent variable (Independent)

The independent variable (Independent) is a variable that influences or causes a change in the dependent variable. The independent variable in this study is the customer perspective (X).

2. Associated Variables (Dependents)

Related variable (Dependent) is the variable that is expected to arise as a result of the independent variable (X). The related variable in this study is customer loyalty (Y).

B. RESEARCH STAGES

- 1) Pre-Field Stage

This stage includes all matters relating to the preparations made by researchers before leaving for the field. Among other things, the research that will be carried out originates from problems within the scope of events that are ongoing or ongoing and can be observed and verified in real terms during the course of the research. Furthermore, in accordance with the issues raised in the research, the research location was chosen to be used as a data source, assuming that in qualitative research, the number (informants) is not too influential than the context. In addition, the researcher also submitted a title that was lifted from an existing problem to the lecturer in Research Methodology course.

- 2) Field Activity Stage

This field activity stage is related to the researchers' efforts to obtain the information needed in the research, namely one of the interviews with researchers who have prepared several questions to gather information from sources.

- 3) Data Analysis Stages

Data analysis in qualitative research begins before the pre-field stage, that means before entering the field, then while in the field and after finishing in the field.

In this case Nasution stated: "The analysis has started since formulating and explaining the problem, before going into the field and continues until the writing of the research results. Data analysis becomes a guide for further

research until, if possible, a grounded theory. However, in qualitative research, data analysis is more focused during the process in the field along with data collection. In fact, data analysis in qualitative research is an ongoing activity that occurs throughout the investigative process rather than after process. In reality, qualitative data analysis takes place during the data collection process rather than after data collection is complete.”

C. RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Research instruments are tools or facilities used by researchers in collecting research data so that their work becomes easier and better, in the sense of being thorough, complete and systematic so that it is easier to process.

The research instrument according to Sugiyono is a tool used to measure natural phenomena and social phenomena that are being observed. From this understanding it can be understood that research instruments are tools used by researchers to measure natural phenomena or social phenomena that are being observed in data collection, so as to facilitate the research process and obtain systematic results.

In this study, the key instruments were the researchers themselves and also non-test research instruments, namely in the form of a questionnaire compiled based on the indicators of the research variables. The indicators are set out in detail in the questions in the form of a questionnaire and distributed to the respondents. In this study, the research instrument is as follows:

Table 1. Variable Indicator

No	Variable	Indicator
1.	Customer Perspective	<i>Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance</i> and Empathy from the customer towards the Shopee application.
2.	Customer loyalty	Customer commitment to stores, brands or suppliers based on a positive attitude which is reflected in the form of consistent repeat purchases.

D. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Population is the subject of research. The population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions. Population according to Maulidi is a collection of individuals or objects that are the subject of discussion or research.

The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. It is also explained that the sample is part or representative of the population being studied. The sample must be representative of the population or representative, meaning that it can maximally describe the state of the population so that the conclusions drawn are correct.

In this study, the population is UNUJA students who use the Shopee marketplace and also the general public who are customers or users of the Shopee application.

The sampling technique used is Purposive Sampling, namely the method of determining samples based on certain criteria or considerations that are in accordance with the research objectives. So that according to the sample criteria in this study there were 33 respondents consisting of:

1. Active students of UNUJA class of 2019 to class of 2022.
2. Communities in Karanganyar village and Bago village who shop at the Shopee marketplace.

E. DATA SOURCES

The type of data needed to obtain information about the variables studied in this study is to use primary data and secondary data.

a) Primary data

Primary data is a data source that is obtained directly or it can be said that data sources directly provide data to data collectors (in this case, namely researchers). In this study, the data was obtained through: distributing questionnaires to predetermined sources.

b) Secondary Data

Secondary data is a data source that does not directly provide data to data collectors (in this case, namely researchers). Secondary data can be in the form of data that is already available and can be obtained by researchers through reading, listening or viewing. The secondary data used in this study were obtained from relevant literature such as journals, reference books, the internet and others.

F. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

Data are units of information recorded by media that are distinguishable from other data, can be analyzed and are relevant to a particular program. Data collection is a systematic and standard procedure to obtain the required data.

The data collection techniques used by the author are:

1. Observation Method

According to Sugiyono, Observation is a complex process, a process composed of various biological and psychological processes. Two of the most important are the processes of observation and memory.

2. Questionnaire Method (Questionnaire)

Questionnaires are a number of written questions that are used to obtain information from respondents in the sense of personal reports or things that they know.

This questionnaire is used to obtain answers to the questions shown to the informant in several alternatives/answers. The resource person is the person who provides feedback or answers the questions asked. Questionnaires are used as a tool to measure or obtain data about the influence of the customer's perspective on the Shopee marketplace.

The author distributes questionnaires to sources via google form. The selected informants are active UNUJA students and the surrounding community who are users of the Shopee marketplace based on indicators of customer satisfaction with services at the Shopee marketplace. The measurement scale taken by the author is the Guttman scale. According to Sugiyono, "The Guttman Scale is a scale used to obtain firm answers from respondents, namely there are only two intervals such as "agree-disagree"; "Yes No"; "True False"; "positive-negative"; "never-never" and so on. In this study, the authors only used the word options 'yes' or 'no' in the answer choices given to respondents. With this type of measurement scale, a clear answer will be obtained, namely between 'yes' or 'no'.

Tabel 2. Measurement Table

No.	Question Items	(%)	(%)
		Answer "YES"	Answer "NO"
1	Is Shopee's service satisfactory?	93.9%	7.1%
2	Is the security of your personal data safe at Shopee?	90.9%	9.1%
3	Are you having trouble shopping using the Shopee app?	18.2%	81.8%
4	Can Customer Service at Shopee solve your problem?	81.8%	18.2%
5	Does Shopee already provide features that help you shop?	100%	0
6	Have you ever experienced fraud when shopping at the Shopee marketplace?	36.4%	63.6%
7	Have you ever experienced a discrepancy in the goods ordered?	75.8%	24.2%
8	Is the seller fast response in serving your purchase?	72.7%	27.3%
9	Have you ever received poor service from sellers at Shopee?	36.4%	63.6%
10	The packaging of the goods you bought does not match the estimated time given.	33.3%	66.7%
11	Did the goods you receive arrive on time?	81.8%	18.2%
12	Has the item you received been damaged?	24.2%	75.8%
13	Is the service provided by the courier friendly?	97%	3%
14	Are you having trouble choosing a freight forwarder?	0%	100%
15	Have you ever experienced that the	24.2%	75.8%

goods ordered did not reach you?

G. DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis according to Miles and Huberman, there are three flow of activities, namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification.

1. Data reduction is defined as a selection process, focusing on simplifying, abstracting, and transforming "rough" data that emerges from field notes. Reduction is carried out since data collection, starting with making summaries, coding, tracing themes, writing memos, and so on, with the intention of eliminating irrelevant data or information, then the data is verified.

2. Presentation of data is a description of a set of structured information that provides the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action. Presentation of qualitative data is presented in the form of narrative text, with the aim of being designed to combine structured information in a coherent and easy-to-understand form.

3. Drawing conclusions or verification is the final activity of qualitative research. Researchers must arrive at conclusions and verify, both in terms of the meaning and truth of the conclusions agreed upon by the place where the research was carried out. The meaning that the researcher formulates from the data must be tested for its correctness, suitability, and robustness. The researcher must realize that in searching for meaning, he must use an emic approach, namely from the point of view of key information, and not the interpretation of meaning according to the researcher's point of view (ethical view).

H. CHECKING THE AUTHENTICITY OF DATA

Sugiyono (2015: 92) states that the technique of checking the validity of the data is the degree of trust in the research data obtained and can be justified for its truth. To check the validity of the data in qualitative research includes the credibility test, transferability test, dependability test and finally the objectivity test.

1) Credibility Test

Credibility test (credibility) is a test of trust in data from qualitative research. This type of testing has two functions, namely the first function is to carry out an examination in such a way with a level of confidence that our findings can be achieved, and the second function is to show the degree of confidence in the results of the findings by proving the multiple facts being studied.

In this study, to check the validity of the data, researchers used a triangulation technique. Where according to Sugiyono (2015: 372) triangulation is a technique of checking the validity of data that combines various data collection techniques and existing data sources, this triangulation utilizes something other than research data, with the aim of checking purposes or as a comparison of the research data obtained .

The type of triangulation used in this research is source triangulation, which uses several data collection techniques on one source only. The data collection techniques used are observation and questionnaires, while the data source itself is through the Shopee application.

2) Transferability Test

Sugiyono (2015: 376) explains that the transferability test is a technique for testing external validity in qualitative research. To apply the transferability test in this study, the researcher will later provide detailed, clear, and systematic descriptions of the research results. The description of the results of the research in detail, clearly and systematically aims to make this research easily understood by others and the results of the research can be applied to the population where the sample in this study was taken.

3) Dependability Test

Sugiyono explained that the dependability test was carried out by auditing the entire research process. In this study the researcher conducted an inspection or audit by way of the researcher consulting back to the supervisor, then the supervisor would audit the entire research process. Furthermore, researchers will also consult with supervisors to reduce mistakes and errors that exist in the presentation of research results and processes during research.

4) Confirmability/Objectivity Test.

According to Sugiyono, the confirmability test is a test of objectivity in quantitative research, research can be said to be objective if this research has been agreed upon by many people. Where researchers will re-examine the data obtained about the customer's perspective regarding business ethics on the Shopee marketplace.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the data in filling out the questionnaire which was distributed online have been filled in by 60 respondents and have fulfilled the required sample data where the results obtained are sufficient to be able to answer how the influence of the customer perspective on customer loyalty on the Shopee marketplace. Some of the points asked are:

Table 3. Field Observation Results

1. Is Shopee's service satisfactory?	The value obtained was 93.9% of respondents answered "Yes" and around 7.1% of respondents answered "No". In terms of Shopee's service, it can be said that its customers are satisfied.
2. Is the security of your personal data safe at Shopee?	The value obtained was 90.9% of respondents answered "Yes" and around 9.1% of respondents answered "No". Shopee here means that it can handle data security from its customers.

3. Are you having trouble shopping using the Shopee app?	The value obtained was 19.2% answered "Yes" and around 81.8% of respondents answered "No". Shopee customers here can easily understand how to use the Shopee application.
4. Can Customer Service at Shopee solve your problem?	The value obtained was that 81.8% of respondents answered "Yes" and 18.2% answered "No". For Shopee Customer Service here, it can be said to be good and able to solve problems from customers.
5. Does Shopee already provide features that help you shop?	The value obtained is 100% of respondents answered "Yes". This means that it can be said that the features contained in the Shopee Application are quite interesting and liked by its customers.
6. Have you ever experienced fraud when shopping at the Shopee marketplace?	The value obtained was 36.4% of respondents answered "Yes" and 63.6% of respondents answered "No". It means that in this case Shopee must be able to deal with things that smell of fraud because from the existing data, it is still quite high. To say that shopping at Shopee is safe.
7. Have you ever experienced a discrepancy in the goods ordered?	The value obtained was that 75.8% of respondents answered "Yes" and 24.2% of respondents answered "No". This can be stated that the shopee and the seller should be able to display pictures and conditions of goods according to customer quality.
8. Is the seller <i>fast response</i> in serving your purchase?	The value obtained was 72.7% of respondents answered "Yes" and 27.3% of respondents answered "No". It means that in this case the seller has been declared good enough in providing loyalty to his customers.
9. Have you ever received poor service from sellers at Shopee?	The results obtained were 36.4% of respondents answered "Yes" and 63.6% of respondents answered "No". In terms of this service, sellers at Shopee should be better at providing their services because from the above values it can still be said that there are still some sellers who are still not good at providing services/
10. The packaging of the goods you bought does not match the estimated time given.	The results obtained were 33.3% of respondents answered "Yes" and 66.7% of respondents answered "No". This can be stated that in terms of the estimated time for packing the goods is quite good and appropriate. But it should also be noted that it is still quite high and the estimated goods ordered do not match the time allotted.

11. Did the goods you receive arrive on time?	The results obtained were 81.8% of respondents answered "Yes" and 18.2% of respondents answered "No". This shows that the goods ordered by the customer come in accordance with a predetermined time.
12. Has the item you received been damaged?	The results obtained were 24.2% of respondents answered "Yes" and 75.8% of respondents answered "No". This shows that most of the goods received by consumers are not damaged. And there are still some that are damaged, from this point of view, the delivery party should be more careful and better in the future. So that the goods ordered are safe and do not suffer significant damage.
13. Is the service provided by the courier friendly?	The results obtained were 97% of respondents answered "Yes" and 3% of respondents answered "No". From these data it is evident that the customer's assessment of the courier is almost perfect, because the courier is friendly in delivering the items ordered.
14. Are you having trouble choosing a freight forwarder?	The results obtained were 0% of respondents answered "Yes" and 100% of respondents answered "No". That according to the data in the Shopee Application it is very easy for customers to choose the expedition they want.
15. Have you ever experienced that the goods ordered did not reach you?	The results obtained were 24.2% of respondents answered "Yes" and 75.8% of respondents answered "No". This can be stated quite well. And some things also need to be fixed because there are some customers who are still experiencing that the goods ordered do not reach the recipient.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Business Ethics on Customer Perspectives

Based on the results obtained from the influence of business ethics on the customer's perspective, it is very significant that if business ethics goes well, it will also have a good impact on the customer's perspective on something. Respondents from Shopee customers can be assessed as quite good where they can fulfill all their needs through this Shopee Application. This also has a good impact on the Shopee company to be able to maintain the perspective of Shopee customers so that in the future it can continue to survive or increase from

before. Shopee itself must continuously issue business innovation and creativity to be able to increase customer perspectives which in turn can increase value or income for the company.

The Effect of Business Ethics on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results obtained, a significant influence of Business Ethics on customer loyalty will increase in line with the maximization of business ethics by sellers towards customers. Business ethics has a role in business activities (Akmala & Ridlwan, 2022). Sellers at Shopee E-Commerce think that this implementation will help consumers meet their needs and can avoid bad behavior. Consumers are respondents who have a high frequency. The majority of respondents have made transactions at Shopee more than 2 to 10 times a month. This shows that respondents have interpreted the existence of the application of business ethics with customer loyalty. Customer loyalty is the key to the success of a company that must be able to improve business ethics because if it increases, customer loyalty will also continue to increase and vice versa. In his business activities, a seller at Shopee not only needs to prioritize the amount of profit or profit but also put forward the convenience aspect between the two parties which can later have an impact on increasing customer loyalty to both the Shopee company and the sellers within Shopee.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results of the research and discussion above it is known that business ethics, customer perspective and customer satisfaction have a positive and quite significant effect on the Shopee *market place*. The business ethics applied by Shopee sellers and services can encourage customers to become loyal. Consumers believe that the existence of business ethics can produce justice and equity between sellers and buyers so that they can generate mutual benefits without either party feeling disadvantaged. Then consumers who are E-commerce users also consider quality services to be able to make consumers loyal customers. And the feeling of satisfaction when shopping *online* is also based on aspects of the need to be able to feel satisfaction that is not excessive and can also encourage someone to become loyal so that they make purchases on E-commerce repeatedly.

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